

Study of Mesomorphic Behaviour of *p*-*n*-Alkyl (*p*'-*n*-Alkoxy)benzoates

Y K. AGRAWAL^a and SADHANA RAJPUT*^b

^aChemistry Department, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-380 009

^bPharmacy Department, Faculty of Technology & Engineering, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

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Twentyfour homologues of two new series, viz. *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxy)benzoates and *p*'-*n*-hexyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxy)benzoates have been studied for their mesomorphic behaviour. The mesomorphism is exhibited over a wide range of temperatures. The homologues exhibit predominantly smectic mesophase showing focal conic textures of smectic-A variety. Few binary mixtures comprising homologues of the first series have also been studied.

A number of mesogenic esters have been synthesised in search of new smectogenic mesogens to explore the polymesomorphism of smectic phases especially for the SmA and SmC phases due to their application in display devices.

Twelve members (methyl to octyl, decyl, dodecyl, tetradecyl and hexadecyl derivatives) of each series, i.e. *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxy)benzoates (Series-I) and *p*'-*n*-hexyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxy)benzoates (Series-II) have been synthesised and their mesomorphic properties studied. These compounds have been synthesised by first treating the *trans*-*p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoic acids² with thionyl chloride and the resultant acid chlorides are then treated with *n*-amyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate and *n*-hexyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate to get the homologues of Series I and II respectively.

Results and Discussion

The mesomorphic properties of both the series prepared are comparable. In both the series, first member, viz. the methyl derivative is monotropic nematic, whereas the second member, i.e. ethyl derivative exhibits smectic and nematic mesophases. Third member of series-I is also polymesomorphic exhibiting smectic as well as nematic mesophases whereas third member of Series-II exhibits only smectic mesophase. From butyl derivative both the series are predominantly smectogenic. The smectic-isotropic transition temperature curve (Figs. 1 and 2) shows odd-even effect. Normally a nematogenic homologues series exhibits falling tendency for *N-I* curve. In the present case both the series exhibit rising smectic-isotropic curve. All the homologues exhibit mesomorphism at relatively lower temperatures (52–78°) and the range of smectic mesophase is quite wide – maximum for hexadecyl derivative (Series-I) is 56° and for decyl derivative (Series-II) 52°. Their thermal stabilities are also comparable. The thermal stabilities and other characteristics of the homologues of Series I and II are compared with other homologues series, viz. *p*-iso-amyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxy)benzoates² (Series-III) and *p*-*n*-amylphenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxy-

Fig. 1 *p*-*n*-Amyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxy)benzoate (●)solid-mesomorphic/isotropic, (Δ)smectic-nematic, (○) nematic-isotropic and (⊗) smectic-isotropic.

namates (Series-IV). The molecular geometry of the series are given in Fig. 3 and a comparison of their thermal stabilities is given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—THERMAL STABILITIES OF SERIES I-IV

	I	II	III	IV
Average S-N or S-I transitions	106.5	104.5	100.7	109.5
	C ₅ -C ₁₄	C ₅ -C ₁₄	C ₅ -C ₁₄	C ₈ -C ₁₄
Average N-I transitions	84.5	84.0	—	127.8
	C ₂ -C ₃	C ₂		C ₁ -C ₁₀
Commencement of smectic mesophase	C ₂	C ₂	C ₁	C ₈

A comparison of the transition temperatures of these series reveals that increase in alkyl chain-length at R' end from *n*-amyl to *n*-hexyl (Series I and II respectively) does not lower the isotropic transition temperatures, and does not affect the smectic and nematic mesophase also. It can

Fig. 2. *p*-*n*-Hexyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate : (●) solid-mesomorphic, (Δ) smectic-nematic, (○) nematic-isotropic and (⊙) smectic-isotropic.

be concluded that once the carbon chain-length is sufficient, addition of one more CH₂ unit does not affect the mesomorphic properties appreciably. However *n*- and *i*-positions of the terminal amyl group in Series I and III respectively, affect the mesomorphic properties due to branching effect. In comparison to alkoxy (OR) group of

Series I : *p*-*n*-Amyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates.

Series II *p*-*n*-Hexyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates.

Series III . *p*-*i*-Amyl (*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates.

Series IV : *p*-*n*-Amyloxyphenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates

Fig. 3.

Series IV, the ester group (COOR) is more conducive to smectic mesophases due to higher polarisability.

All the three binary phase diagrams show that the eutectic points are obtained at much lower temperatures and the mesophase length is increased appreciably. In binary phase diagram (Fig. 4) the monotropic nematic mesophase is converted to enantiotropic nematic over a wide concentration range.

Fig. 4. System . *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*'-ethoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate : *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*'-amylalkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate

The study has provided lot of new mesogens exhibiting nematic and smectic mesophases.

Experimental

The *trans*-*p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamic acids prepared² were converted to their respective acid chlorides⁴. The acid chlorides (0.01 mol) were heated on a water-bath with dry *n*-alkyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate (0.01 mol) dissolved in dry pyridine (8 ml) for 10 min and then cooled overnight. It was acidified with dilute HCl and cooled in an ice-bath. The product thus obtained was washed with dilute NaOH (0.01N), then with water and crystallised from alcohol as fine white needles or powder (50%). Transition temperatures of these homologues are recorded in Tables 2 and 3.

TABLE 2-*p*-*n*-AMYL (*p*'-*n*-ALKOXYCINNAMOYLOXY)BENZOATES

n-Alkyl group	Transition temp. (°C)		
	S	N	I
Methyl	—	(76.0)*	88.0
Ethyl	(86.0)	87.0	97.5
Propyl	78.0	82.0	87.5
Butyl	72.0	—	105.0
Amyl	75.0	—	103.0
Hexyl	76.0	—	107.5
Heptyl	60.0	—	105.0
Octyl	65.5	—	108.0
Decyl	58.0	—	108.0
Dodecyl	70.0	—	107.5
Tetradecyl	55.0	—	107.5
Hexadecyl	52.0	—	108.0

* Indicates monotropy.

TABLE 3—*p*'-*n*-HEXYL (*p*'-*n*-ALKOXYCINNAMOYLOXY)BENZOATES

n-Alkyl group	Transition temp. (°C)		
	S	N	I
Methyl	—	(67.0)*	78.0
Ethyl	54	84.0	90.0
Propyl	(85.0)	—	92.0
Butyl	75.0	—	100.0
Amyl	68.0	—	97.0
Hexyl	65.0	—	103.0
Heptyl	78.0	—	103.5
Octyl	58.0	—	106.0
Decyl	56.0	—	108.0
Dodecyl	52.0	—	106.5
Tetradecyl	55.0	—	107.0
Hexadecyl	56.0	—	107.0

* Indicates monotropy.

The mesomorphic behaviour of the compounds was studied on a Laborlux-Leitz 12 polarising microscope fitted with heating arrangement. The purity of the compounds was checked by elemental analysis and infrared spectra.

Fig. 5. System : *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*'-methoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate : *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*'-ethoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate.

Evaluation of mesomorphism : Smectic mesophases of the compounds were identified by miscibility studies using the known references :

(i) *p*-*n*-Propyl phenyl ester of *p*-*n*-amyloxybenzoic acid⁵,

(ii) *p*-*n*-Hexadecyloxybenzoic acid⁵,

(iii) *p*-*n*-Dodecyloxybenzoic acid⁵,

and the mesophase was found to be of smectic A variety.

Preparation of binary mixtures : The binary mixtures were prepared by method already reported in literature⁶. Following binary systems were studied :

System 1 : (a) *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*-methoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate

(b) *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*-ethoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate

System 2 : (a) *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*-ethoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate

(b) *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*-amyloxybenzoate)

System 3 : (a) *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*-proxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate

(b) *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*-butoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate

The phase transition curves of Systems 1, 2 and 3 are plotted in Figs. 5, 3 and 6 respectively.

Fig. 6. System : *p*-*n*-Amyl (*p*'-*n*'-proxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate : *p*-*n*-amyl (*p*'-*n*'-butoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoate.

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